

Zambia, A Country with Rich Mineral Resources and Arable Land Yet Poor

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Abstract: The purpose of the study was to assess the reasons why Zambia, a country endowed with mineral resources and arable land still ranks among the countries with the highest levels of poverty globally and the study sought to investigate whether colonialism, dependency syndrome, governance and other factors impact negatively on her development. The study employed a mixed paradigm and descriptive survey design that sampled Institutions of higher learning, Parliament, Political Parties without representation in Parliament, Government Ministries and Non-Governmental Organizations and interviewed, members of parliament, senior civil servants, university lecturers and NGO members. Data was obtained from respondents by means of interviews, questionnaires and project observation schedules. The sample consisted of two hundred respondents. Frequency, percentages, tables, graphs and pie-charts were used to analyze the quantitative and qualitative data obtained. Data was then analyzed manually in some cases and also, a combination of software MS Access and MS Excel. The findings revealed that Zambia exports raw materials, rampant corruption and relies on foreign aids which benefits more the donors than the recipients and leads to debt accumulation and the study recommended that the Zambia should add value to its exports, eliminate corruption and use aid on capital investments.

Keywords: Arable Land, Development, Mineral Resources, Poor, Poverty, and Rich.

1. INTRODUCTION

The area of modern Zambia is known to have been inhabited by the Khoisan and Batwa peoples until around AD 300 when migrating Bantu began to settle around these areas. On 24th October, 1964, the former protectorate of Northern Rhodesia became the Republic of Zambia, ending 73 years of British rule and became a sovereign state and changed its name to Zambia, taking its name from the Zambezi river and the first Republican President was Kenneth David Kaunda Lusaka is the capital city of the country (Walubita, 2015). Since independence in 1964, Zambia has been ruled by Four political parties (UNIP, MMD, PF and UPND) and seven Republican Presidents; Kenneth Kaunda, Fredrick Chiluba, Levy Mwanawasa, Rupiah Banda, Michael Sata, Edgar Lungu and now Hakainde Hichilema.

Zambia is a landlocked country at the crossroads of Central, Southern and East Africa and is between Angola in the West, Namibia, Botswana and Zimbabwe in the South, Mozambique, Malawi and Tanzania in the East and the Democratic Republic of Congo in the North. Zambia is mostly a high plateau 3,000 to 5,000 feet above sea level and is drained by two major river basins; the Zambezi/Kafue basin in the centre, east and south covering about three quarters of the country and the Congo basin in the North covering about one-quarter of the country. The vegetation of Zambia is categorized into four main types; closed forests, woodlands or open forests, termitaria and grasslands while the soil composition is silt, sand and clay plus humus. The annual rainfall in Zambia averages between 700mm in the South and 1,400mm in the North (Marja and CSO, 2011).

The current population of Zambia is 20,569,737 in 2023, a 2.7% increase from 2022 and is with about 73 different tribes with a wide cultural diversity (Centar Statistical Office, 2017). The 2020 census indicated that Zambia's most widely spoken languages are Bemba (spoken by 35% of the population), Nyanja or Chewa (20%), Tonga (12%) and Lozi (6%) while an urban variety of Nyanja (Chewa) is the lingua franca of the Capital, Lusaka and is used for communication between speakers of different languages. The Government of the Republic of Zambia, through the Education Act of 2011 and subsequent Primary Literacy Programme (PLP) has designated seven local languages of instruction to be used in schools in the country; Chitonga, Cinyanja, Ibibemba, Kikaonde, Lunda, Silozi and Luvale (Englund, 2013). Zambia produces copper, cobalt, gold, diamonds, nickel, manganese, emeralds, beryllium, myriad gemstones, sulfur, zinc, coal, iron ore, steel, limestone, uranium and other platinum group metals and Zambia is internationally recognized as a major producer of copper and cobalt (ranked as the seventh and second highest world producer respectively). It also produces precious metals (gold, silver), gemstones (amethyst, aquamarine, emerald and tourmaline), coal and industrial minerals. Copper and Cobalt are among Zambia's main exports while non-traditional exports include cotton, coffee, fresh flowers, burley tobacco, gemstones and maize among others (Gordon, 2012).

Zambia holds much of Southern Africa's arable land and internal renewable fresh water source while the geographical features of Zambia include land forms, bodies of water, climate, soils, natural vegetation and animal life. Zambia is a raw slice of Africa friendly and with many unspoilt wild places worthy of any pioneers. Nevertheless, Zambia ranks among the countries with the highest levels of poverty and inequality globally (ranked 127th in 2023) (Malcon et al, 2019).

Britain colonized Zambia from the late 1888 until 24th October, 1964 and the main reasons for Zambia's colonization were mainly economic, political and religious. The objectives of colonialism were political domination, making possible the exploitation of the colonized countries and in the process and imposition of European religion. (Mulenga, 2017). In the process, the Africans lost their political independence, some traditional political institutions were destroyed and replaced with foreign ones and foreign culture and languages were imposed on Africans without regard for their own culture and language.

The colonization of Zambia has contributed to economic, social and political underdevelopment by spurring ethnic-tainted civil conflict and discrimination and by shaping the ethnic composition, size, shape and landlocked status of the newly independent state (Walubita, 2015). The negative effects of colonialism is degradation of natural resources, economic instability, ethnic rivalries, human rights violations, capitalism, urbanization, introduction of foreign diseases to livestock and humans, dehumanized Zambian labour force and traders, making Zambia as a British protectorate dependent by introducing a mono-cultural economy for the protectorate and also, by plundering Zambia's resources and carving it up into an artificial state The British colonial power created vicious cycles of violence, poverty and authoritarianism that are playing out to this day.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

In spite of the numerous mineral resources, arable land, internal renewable fresh water source and external support to the country, Zambia still ranks among the countries with the highest levels of poverty and inequality globally (World Bank, 2019).

1.2. The Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to assess the reasons why Zambia, a country endowed with mineral resources and arable land still ranks among the countries with the highest levels of poverty globally.

1.3. Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

- Investigate the negative effects of colonialism on the development of Zambia.
- Assess the impact of good governance and rule of law on Zambia's development.
- Establish the effects of the use of a foreign language and its effect on the development of Zambia.

1.4. Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the Dependency theory first proposed by Augustine the economist and the statesman Prebisch (1950's) which is an idea that resources flow from a "periphery" of poor and underdeveloped states to a "core" of wealthy states, enriching the latter at the expense of the former. Actually, dependency theory is a sociological theory which holds that economic events in history have encouraged developing countries to depend upon the support of more advanced nations (Fischer, 2015) and Theotonio Dos Santos, one of the founders of dependency theory describes dependence as "a situation in which the economy of certain countries is conditioned by the development and expansion of another economy to which the former is subjected" (Dos Santos, 2010c).

1.5. Significance of the Study

It is hoped that the findings of the study would be of help to all the stake holders interested in the development of Zambia. It would benefit the current government in power, opposition leaders, intellectuals, Non-governmental Organizations and the community members in continuously reviewing the programmes, organize their economy and work differently so as to come up with appropriate interventions in order to revamp the economy of Zambia. The policy makers would benefit as the study would help them modify the economic system to make it more relevant to national needs. The findings would also help politicians and government officials to create favourable local policies for local investors, strengthen legislature, executive and judicial systems to enhance effectiveness and efficiency in governance as well as awaken the citizens to hold leadership accountable to the electorates.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Colonization of Zambia

Zambia's colonization began in 1888 when the British South African Company (BSAC) secured mineral rights in the area. It became a British Protectorate in 1899, being governed as part of Barotziland-North-Western Rhodesia (Taylor, 2018). By 1889, Britain had established control over the area, administering it using the British South African Company, which managed the region on behalf of the Crown by signing treaties with several indigenous leaders and the area we now call Zambia became Northern Rhodesia in 1911. In 1924, the British Colonial Office took control of Northern Rhodesia as a Territory from BSAC and Kalomo was the first capital of Zambia but gave way to Livingstone in 1907 and then to Lusaka in 1935, when the country became what was now known as Northern Rhodesia Colony. The Federation of Rhodesia and Nyasaland (Zimbabwe, Zambia and Malawi) was created between August 1st and October 23, 1953 and lasted until December 31, 1963 and Zambia became an independent country on 24th October, 1964 (Englund, 2013).

Zambia was colonized by the British from 1888 to 1964 and (Breunig, 2014) says, "in simple terms, colonialism is described as an act of practicing full or partial control over another country." This was done after the conquest of decentralized and centralized indigenous leaders and then the British colonial power set about establishing the colonial state system. The reasons for colonization were mainly economic, political and religious and the first objective of colonialism was political domination and its second objective was to make possible the exploitation of the colonized country. The major reasons however, for colonization of Zambia by the British were to search for new markets, the need to obtain raw materials such as copper, cobalt, diamonds, gold, timber, etc and export these resources, the desire to invest surplus capital outside Britain and the claim that Zambians and other Africans needed to be civilized through Western education and religion. Ultimately, the British also wanted to protect their trade routes (Gordon, 2012).

2.2 Negative effects of colonization of Zambia

The negative effects of colonialism were environmental degradation of natural resources, the spread of diseases, economic instability ethnic rivalries, human rights violations urbanization and it made the Colony of Zambia dependent by introducing a mono-cultural economy for the territory. The colonial power also dehumanized African labour force and traders and forced them to work in colonial mines at very low wages and displaced them from their land (Mulenga, 2017). In addition, Africans lost their political independence, some traditional political institutions were destroyed and replaced with foreign ones and foreign culture was imposed on Africans without regard for their own culture. The colonization of Zambia has contributed to economic, social and political underdevelopment by spurring ethnic-tainted discrimination and by shaping the ethnic composition, size, shape and status of people in independent Zambia (Taylor, 2018). In Zambia today, the language used in

government, education and media is the one imposed by the colonial power though most people speak their native Zambian languages. and arguably, Zambia as a poor country lags because of modern age colonialism which severely affects its economic growth and development.

2.3 Language Western Ideal of Domination

Unlike others, language is the real western ideal that is used to dominate other nations, African nations and Zambia in particular. In response to Alan Davies's review article 'Ironizing the Myth of Linguicism' (2010), Nordhoff, 2012 in his Realities and Myths of Linguistic imperialism (1997) summarizes principles for the analysis of linguistic imperialism and demonstrates that the phenomenon is far from mythical. It is real and a destructive one. According to Edward Said, one of the cultural aspect in Africa that is at its agony is Language. To him, the linguistic legacy that imperialism has bequeathed to Africa, and the ways in which this inheritance is being enjoyed down to the present, [especially through the sector of education], is a real imperialism. Therefore, Linguistic imperialism is not a simple matter as many think. (Austin and Sallabank, 2011; Maptia, 2021).

What is really meant by linguistic imperialism? Linguistic imperialism is a subtype of linguicism. As it is discussed in (Everett, 2012), Tove coined the term in order to illustrate the resemblances between the social distinctions or discrimination based on 'race' or ethnicity (racism, ethnicism), gender (sexism) and language (linguicism). Therefore, as Phillipson observes, linguicism studies attempt to put the sociology of language and education into a certain form of study aiming to demonstrate how language contributes to unequal access to societal power and show how linguistic hierarchies operate and how they are legitimated. Many scholars on the continent use the terms 'language spread' and 'language death' to explain why African language users speak languages such as English, French, Spanish, and others and why other languages are being abandoned. These scholars do so in order to minimize the effects and the systematic imperialism through language by western civilizations. However, historical records as (Deutscher, 2010) argue and prove to the contrary. Zealous African and Indian sociolinguists have specifically contributed to identifying the mechanisms and ideologies of linguistic imperialism. The evidence that linguistic imperialism is not just a term by linguists without proper evidences that a person or a nation can systematically dominate another is the human rights law, which decrees that discrimination based on such features as race, gender and language is morally unjustifiable (Rice, 2009).

2.4 Channels for Linguistic Imperialism

Linguistic imperialism' is connected to a multitude of activities, ideologies and structural relationships. It takes place within an overarching structure of asymmetrical relations between the west and the third world, where, according to many linguists, language interlocks with other dimensions, cultural (particularly in education, science and the media), economic and political systems (Evans, 2010).

Education: The only simple way to impose linguistic domination is through education. The reason is simple. Education is a vital site for social and linguistic reproduction. It is a real ground for the inculcation of relevant knowledge, skills and attitudes, and therefore particularly central in processes of linguistic hierarchization (CSO, 2017).

The selection of the language of instruction: most of the languages used in the African systems of education are from the former colonizer. Children, in most instances, are not allowed to use their familiar or mother tongue at school. This practice makes the African learners in the African classes by African teachers admit that African languages are inferior. The result is that they abandon them and do not want to use them anymore. The same attitude toward African languages in education, can lead to school dropouts, skipping lessons, and many other negative consequences.

Books or learning materials written in the master's language: when the language of instruction is selected what follow is the development of learning and teaching materials. These are written in the language that both the teacher and the learner do not use frequently at home, which implies that African children, learn how to read and write not in their own languages but in a foreign language. They become literate (doubtfully) in the master's language and illiterate in their ancestor's language.

Research to be conducted and published in the same language: concerning research at any level of their education in any domain, African learners are required to conduct and present their research work in the language that is not theirs. They imitate their lecturers, professors who also have imitated the master. The cycle is continuous (Sotelo, 2018).

Media (all forms): media are strong institutions for languages. Their input contains large data of linguistic choices and forms that people consume instantly. Most TV shows and radio programs are in English, French, and so on and only a few are in African languages. Media choose the language that people should listen to and use.

Entertainment is another route of linguistic imperialism through media. Most of the entertainment that African adults (women in particular) and children view or play are not in their mother tongue. The cartoons, for example, are in English at a very large scale. Media, especially the TV, is the main source of these cartoons. African children consume English even before they are the age to go to school.

Economy (globalization): It is common today to hear people holding the argument of the world getting smaller by technology and globalization and to them it justifies the use of foreign languages rather than African languages as languages of education, official affairs and business in African countries. People with such views, often see African languages as a handicap to development. To them there is no significance of African languages in the era of globalization.

Politics and Diplomatic Relations: today many African countries have gained their freedom. They are no longer under the oppression of colonization. However, as it is for African education systems, media, and business, the African political system is another route where western ideals pass through to reach the African continent and one of such is the linguistic imperialism (Breunig, 2014).

As Philipson noted, unlike the brute force of the colonial period (imposition of the master's language, corporal punishment for using one's mother tongue), in postcolonial days' *language policy is much more a matter for negotiation and persuasion*. It requires legitimation, which is how it is rooted. Three important areas in African political systems are under linguistic imperialism:

The notion of official language: Languages such French, English, Portuguese, and so on, are legitimized with a label of Official language. An official language by virtue of law is worthy to serve in political affairs, foreign relations and other offices. The excuse until today has been the African multilingualism.

African constitutions: these codes of laws, which are vital for any political and social organization of any country in the world, are written in French, English and so on. This fact is an undeniable evidence that linguistic imperialism is real and not a mere claim by linguists as many argue.

Political discourses and those by other African stakeholders: except some rare occasions and in some African lands, it is a tradition for African leaders and intellectuals to address their fellow compatriots in foreign languages. The speech of their fathers has been rejected as not worthy addressing important issues such as those concerning the country. In certain situation, the choice of English, French and Portuguese is because; the educated people are no longer able to express themselves freely and fluently in their African languages.

2.5. Effects of the Linguistic Imperialism

The effects of linguistic imperialism in the education sector can lead to many negative outcomes. These effects are not limited to academic performance but extend to other aspects of life. Here, are the easily remarkable or discernable ones:

Poor literacy, numeracy and other academic (even craft) skills: UNESCO estimates that 40 percent of the world's children do not have access to education in *a language they understand*. Therefore, as findings from myriad learning assessments have highlighted, this explains the failure of school systems to support children's acquisition of *literacy, numeracy and other critical skills*.

According to the *Handbook on Language of Instruction Issues in Reading Programs*, while many factors contribute to this learning crisis, *language is increasingly, and rightly, recognized as a key reason that millions of learners globally do not acquire the skills they need to succeed in school and in life*. This is true in Africa where many school systems continue to use *languages for instruction* that children do not speak, use fluently or understand.

Poor Research and less Publication: not only students in African schools conduct less research and publish less, but their instructors also face the same challenge. Though reasons are multiple, the most dominant is language. They are requested to produce works in a language they do not use in their thinking process (French, English, Portuguese, etc.) (Maptia, 2021).

Poor Social life: the impact of linguistic imperialism in education and communities can be summarized by these words by Anderson stating that *educated men are isolated by schooling and by career, mobility from the life of their natal communities, losing progressively understanding of the local affairs from which emerge relationships that administrators must deal with.*

True are those words. The educated man in Africa finds himself unable to properly communicate and understand his own people. The reason is simple. He now thinks differently because he speaks differently. Language shapes the way we think. Speaking a second language means putting on a new personality and identity (Nordhoff, 2012). A similar suggestion is contained in Biobaku's contention that African education that will integrate the African into his community is yet to be discovered.

2.6 Dependence Syndrome

(Fischer, 2015) defines dependency as, "the state of relying on or being controlled by someone or something." Africa and Zambia inclusive was colonized by European states between 1800-1960's and colonialism made African colonies dependent by introducing a mono-cultural economy for the territories. Today, however, the principal powers involved in modern colonization of Africa are Britain, France, Germany, Portugal, Spain and Italy and in nearly all African countries today, the language used in government and media is the one imposed by a recent colonial power and also, foreign aid leads to dependency by most African countries (Kay, 2019a).

The prime dependency is economic dependence which often comes with political dependency, as developed nations are able to use their assistance to influence the political landscape and this is especially worse in our young democracy suffering from corruption and lack of civil rights. Nevertheless, the underdevelopment of developing countries, Zambia inclusive is not naturally inherited, rather it was imposed by the very development of industrialized nations. Therefore, the view that global poverty results from colonialization and exploitation of the poorest nations by the richest nations and by multinational corporations which may be considered a conflict explanation of global inequality (Seshamani, 2010).

Zambia's debt trap makes it accumulate large amounts of debt and interest and the adaptation of policies tailored to the interests of stronger countries may inhibit the weaker regional counties' domestic growth, speed environmental destruction or create temporary growth that precludes sustainable development. Moreover, dependencies have a direct impact on the progress of product development and arise frequently in cross-functional product and education stands accused as the major instrument of this behavioral manipulation (Dreher & Lohmann, 2015). Westernization has stripped many of the cultures that make up Zambians of their knowledge bases, knowledge of tradition and pride in culture. Some high points of European influence include the introduction of Christianity and colonial education, impact on the civilizing mission, cultural alienation and colonial mentality. Because people are more proud of Western culture, this results in the degradation of the sense of belonging to local culture which leads to the loss of national identity and also, westernization causes people to become more consumptive towards imported products (Sotelo, 2018).

2.7 Why is Zambia Poor

Zambia produces and exports a number of minerals and farm produce but still, many Zambians still live in extreme poverty and significant challenges hamper the country's development including limited economic diversification, degradation of the natural resource base, high unemployment, low agricultural productivity, inadequate road and energy infrastructure. How then did Zambia become poor? Trade has declined and droughts have impacted agriculture which has worsened the conditions of farmers as agriculture plays a central role in Zambia's economy, accounting for more than 49% percent of employment in both formal and informal sector (David, 2012). The attitude of people is also a major contributor to poverty in Zambia as most people believe in white color jobs, formal employment, like luxurious lives and that they would be unable to carry out development programmes and afford high standards of living. Also, the Zambian economy is heavily dependent on copper mining and rain-fed agricultural production, which expose the economy to external vulnerabilities such as variances in global copper prices and increasingly erratic seasonal weather patterns (World Bank, 2020).

Zambia is struggling with debt burden and in 1986, the Zambian Government could not secure finance from elsewhere, was forced to borrow from 15 Page 23 commercial banks. However, the terms demanded by the banks were highly onerous and damaged Zambia's development prospects yet further. Zambia became one of the world's most impoverished countries in the world after reckless lending by Western banks caused decades of debt and stagnation and in 2020, Zambia was the first

African country to default in COVID-19 era and it has struggled to finish restructuring external debt that reached \$18.6 billion at the end of 2022 (IMF, 2022). Of Zambia's external debt, 46% is owed to private lenders, 22% to China, 8% to other government and 18% to multilateral institutions and in 2021, the national debt of Zambia increased by 1.4 billion U.S dollars (+5.58 percent) since 2020. With 26.48 billion U. S dollars, the national debt thereby reached its highest value in the observed period (Seshamani, 2010).

2.8 Zambia's Debt and Economic Development

Zambia's economy rebounded in 2021, with real GDP growing at 4.6% from a contraction of 2.8% in 2020, supported by firmer copper prices, favourable external demand, good rainfall and post-election market confidence. With debt servicing costs amounting to 30 percent of the national budget, Zambia's debt weakens the economy by forcing the government to spend money on interest payments when it should be spending on national development. Zambia is in debt distress and urgently needs deep and comprehensive debt treatment in line with the joint WB-IMF Debt Sustainability Analysis (DSA) that called for \$8.4 billion in debt relief in 2022-2025 and additional relief through 2031. Hence, debt relief between now and 2025 would help stabilize Zambia's foreign reserves and keep debt servicing at sustainable levels as IMF put it (Tang & Bundhoo, 2017).

Can aid help Zambia's problems? If perhaps well utilized it can but sometimes aid is given as loans, which only leads to debt accumulation. By supporting economic growth in Zambia, donor countries help create better, stronger and more resilient markets for their exports and in addition, donor programmes benefit supply chains of strategic importance to specific donor country industries that rely on key imports from Zambia for their production (IMF, 2022). Thus aid can reproduce existing inequalities between developed countries and developing countries instead of helping developing countries solve long-term problems. To sum up, there are many barriers in the real world which have led to foreign aid not being able to solve long term problems for aid recipient countries and Zambia is no exception.

2.9 How to Develop the Economy

Donor agencies and organizations are in business and are like local shylocks (kaloba) who rely on given credits to people for their business to thrive. Donor countries and organizations make profits out of whatever assistance they give to Zambia and would not let off this business as the economic development of Zambia would be a loss on their part (Jorg, 2016). At the moment, Zambia has a complex array of existing relationships in key sectors of the economy; mining, agriculture, infrastructure civil society and SME sector where international and regional actors have dominated and large parts of Zambia's formal economy are already highly international. Our Zambian politics are externally influenced and this also complicates relationships within and outside the nation. Infrastructure underdevelopment remains a major challenge to growth, economic diversification and human development and the country loses more revenue from illegal tax evasion and unspecified amount in tax incentives (Hu and Yao, 2019).

Nevertheless, the industrialization of Zambia potentially has the capacity to overcome economic dependency and other complications related to economic development as (Dos Santos, 2010c) observed that, "the industrialization of dependent countries potentially has the capacity to overcome economic dependency." As Dos Santos has alluded to, dependent economies like Zambia need to obtain a high degree of productivity autonomy and develop an important sector of machines and industrialized raw materials and by convincing the elite from within the country to invest in their home nation instead of conspicuous consumption. Farmer Input Support Programme (FISP) and Fertilizer Support Programme (FSP) are good initiatives at reducing poverty but funds to these and other programmes like social cash transfer must be internally sourced instead of depending on donors. The benefits of supporting local farmers however, are that locally grown food supports the local economy as well as strengthening the community as local foods means a safer food supply. Zambia should insist on value addition to raw materials, empower citizens to own industries and mines as well as exploration of minerals and should set up industries for the production of machinery, equipment and spare parts to be used in industry (UNDP, 2010).

First and foremost, government should put in place legislative and policy approaches to prevent commercial and international actors from engaging in exploitative practices, dominate business and ensure that local people benefit but not disincentivizing investment. As the foreign investment money pours in, the government should begin to focus on developing its human resources in addition to its infrastructure. The country should set up many technical and skills schools to give specialized education and if possible pay international corporations and technocrats to train Zambian unskilled workers in

the manufacturing of machines and equipment for mining, industry and agriculture. Above all, civil service to implement laws and policies must not be appointed on political lines but be selected and promoted on merit, experience, seniority, qualification and if possible through an examination (Briggs, 2018).

Industrialization would catapult the nation's development trajectory and manufacturing should become the main driver of growth and then create a stable economy with no foreign debt, high government revenue and a consistently positive surplus (David, 2012). The Zambian economy can mainly be driven by exports in manufactures products from copper such as wires, industrial machinery, electrical and electrical devices, generators, transformers among others, manufactured agricultural products such as animal feed, farmed fish, honey, among others and tourism. In addition, the Zambian economy should be open and free-market economy with dirigiste characteristics and it must be corrupt free, not politicized as well as pro-business with an efficient regulatory environment, competitive tax regime, transparent with efficiency of service. Further, it must have a highly flexible labour market, equal treatment of foreign and domestic investors, empower local investors, create strong international trading links and a highly effective legal system (Foil, 2014).

2.10 Zambian Leadership

Zambia needs selfless leadership who have the distinction and consistency, are ready to sacrifice for the electorates and who should look at themselves as not being superior to the people they lead and not look at themselves as having the monopoly of knowledge and wisdom. Above all, a leadership who would deny themselves and not bent at accumulating wealth, uphold tradition and pride in culture and resist high points of European influence which includes cultural alienation and colonial mentality (Sotelo, 2018). There is need to get mindset right and develop interest of Zambia and stop investing in Western countries, building and buying mansions in Western countries as well as banking in offshore accounts instead of their own country. Zambia has the youngest population of the world and is one of the richest in Africa with the world's fastest growing economies, it remains one of the world's poorest countries with poor living conditions as over 60% of the population live under the poverty line and to change this paradox, education stands accused as the major instrument to break it. Government must open opportunities to every child to access quality education that will allow them address challenges in the 21st century. To achieve this, government should take the burden of financing education and be made free from kindergarten to tertiary level (Erbeznik,2011) There is need to change the philosophy and curricular and promote the teaching of science, technology and engineering. Zambia should not depend on developed counties to finance education but come up with policies not dependent on outsiders but on themselves. To do this, government must eliminate corruption and come up with intelligent arrangements to those exploiting natural resources as well as curb illicit means so that wealth is used on behalf of the people and in the development of Sub-Sahara Africa and not outside.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Study Design

The research design was descriptive survey with both qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection in order to attain the comprehensive results. Qualitative methods were appropriate to this investigation as it produced detailed data from a small group of participants, while exploring feelings, impressions and judgments. On the other hand, quantitative method made the use of questionnaires, surveys and experiment to gather data that is revised and tabulated in numbers, which allows the data to be characterized by use of statistical analysis.

3.2. Research Site

The study was carried out in five institutions of Parliament, Political parties' secretariats, Government ministries, Universities, and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO) offices from which respondents were also sampled.

3.3. Population, Sample and Sampling Procedure

The population for the study was purposefully drawn from the Lusaka province of Zambia where all the respondents are found. Purposive sampling procedure was used to select the institutions (5) while the simple random sampling procedure was used to select the University lecturers (40); twenty from each institution, Members of Parliament (60); twenty from two Political parties with representation in Parliament and independent members, Senior Political party members without representation in Parliament (60); twenty from each party, Senior Civil servants from ministries (20)' two from each Ministry and NGO executive members (20); four from each organization. The sample size comprised of 200 respondents. Also, the primary data was complimented by the secondary data which was derived from government policy documents, ministerial reports and relevant literature on language use.

In the sampling of province and institutions, the study adopted the stratified cluster random sampling technique. Sampling of the province was done on the basis of concentration of respondents and institutions were then done zone by zone. Universities and other institutions were clustered by zones. Two zones were purposively selected based on the basis of concentration of respondents. The sampling was done at three levels: Sampling zones, universities and other institutions- level 1, Sampling University lecturers and Civil servants-level 2, Sampling Members of Parliament, Political party officials and NGO members-level 3.

3.4. Data Analysis

In this research, data was analysed qualitatively as in-depth interviews, questionnaires and observation schedules were used as data collection instruments. Thematic approach was used, where data analysis started with the categorization of themes from the structured interviews, and questionnaires (Kombo and Tromp ,2006). Charts and graphs were used to analyse data. The data gathered was analyzed according to the themes of the study and per the order of the research objectives. Data generated from the interview guide was analyzed manually and also, a combination of software MS Access, SPSS and MS Excel was used to analyze data. Analysis was mainly descriptive, that is, mean, median, mode, range, and standard deviation. Related statistics were applied where possible.

3.5. Ethical Issues

The study avoided pressuring respondents to take part in the research. Alternatively, permission consents, assents were obtained from respondents involved in the research and the research topic was strategically selected to ensure that there was no harm whatsoever to the research respondents. In this research, the study was fully conscious of the need to abide by the ethical rule of respecting the privacy of individuals taking part in the research. In the same way, all the respondents of the research were to remain unidentified to the public as all their valuable views, opinions and perceptions were only known by the researchers for use only in the research and participant’s identities will forever remain hidden.

The Researcher got permission from the Vice Chancellors to interview lecturers, from the Speaker to interview members of parliament, Party secretary generals to interview senior party members, Permanent secretaries to interview senior civil servants and Executive officers to interview NGO members. The names of respondents would remain anonymous for the sake of confidentiality, (Bryman,2001) and (Diener and Crandall,2008). However, the identity of respondents was concealed in the article but for identification in the article, the sixty MPs were allocated numbers 1 to 60, the sixty Party members were allocated ordinal numbers 1st to 60th, the forty University lecturers were allocated names of Primary schools in Lusaka, the twenty Civil servants were allocated letters A to T, the twenty NGO members were allocated names of secondary schools in Lusaka while Zones and institutions used pseudo names.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following findings and discussions were presented according to set research objectives:

4.1. Negative Effects of Colonialism

The study revealed that colonialism has a variety of effects on Zambia and its economic emancipation which among others are dependency syndrome (78.4%), Accumulation of debt (73.6%), Urbanization (69.7%), Distraction of culture (53.6) and Degradation of natural resources (49.6%) as illustrated in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Showing The Distribution of Negative Effect of Colonialism on Zambia

Effects of colonialism	Percentage	
	Yes	No
Dependency syndrome	78.4%	21.6%
Accumulation of debt	73.6%	26.4%
Urbanization	69.7%	30.3%
Distraction of culture	53.6%	46.4%
Degradation of natural resources	49.6%	50.4%

Colonialism had profound and lasting negative effects on Zambia, impacting various aspects of its socio-economic and cultural fabric. One of the most significant consequences was the exploitation of Zambia's natural resources, particularly copper, by colonial powers for their own economic gain. This led to environmental degradation, disruption of local communities, and the impoverishment of the indigenous population. The imposition of arbitrary borders during the colonial era also resulted in the fragmentation of ethnic groups and traditional societies, leading to enduring tensions and conflicts. Furthermore, the introduction of European cultural norms and institutions often marginalized and undermined indigenous practices, eroding the social cohesion that existed prior to colonial rule. The legacy of colonialism in Zambia includes economic inequality, social disintegration, and a struggle for cultural identity, all of which continue to pose challenges for the nation's development and reconciliation. On negative effects of colonialism on Zambia and its economic emancipation, the study revealed that colonialism has contributed to economic, social and political underdevelopment by spurring ethnic-tainted discrimination and by shaping the ethnic composition, size, shape and landlocked status of the independent state (Englund, 2013). The negative effects of colonialism is degradation of natural resources, economic instability, ethnic rivalries, human rights violations, capitalism, urbanization, introduction of foreign diseases to livestock and humans, economic instability, distraction of traditional social, political and economic structures and trade, making the country dependent by debt accumulation and introducing a mono-cultural economy for the territory and also, by plundering Zambia's resources and carving it up into artificial ethnic boundaries, the British colonial power created vicious cycles of hostilities among ethnic groupings, poverty and authoritarianism that are playing out to this day (Foil, 2014). Further, the study reviewed that by supporting economic growth in Zambia, donor countries help create better, stronger and more resilient markets for their exports and in addition, donor programmes benefit supply chains of strategic importance to specific donor country industries that rely on key imports from Zambia for their production (Bitzer, 2018). Thus aid can reproduce existing inequalities between developed countries and developing countries instead of helping developing countries solve long-term problems. Colonialism has created income and wealth inequalities, weak governmental structures and religious conflicts. To sum up, there are many barriers in the real world which have led to foreign aid not being able to solve long term problems for aid recipient countries and Zambia is no exception.

4.2 Impact of Good Governance and Rule of Law on Development

In Zambia, the impact of good governance and the rule of law on development is pivotal in shaping the nation's progress and prosperity. Good governance, characterized by transparency, accountability, and effective institutions, fosters an environment conducive to sustainable development. When leaders adhere to the rule of law, it ensures that policies are implemented fairly, justice is upheld, and citizens' rights are protected. In Zambia, these principles have the potential to curb corruption, promote economic stability, and attract foreign investment. A well-functioning legal framework and institutions contribute to a stable business environment, encouraging entrepreneurship and fostering economic growth. Additionally, good governance enhances social services, such as education and healthcare, promoting human development and overall well-being. Therefore, by prioritizing good governance and the rule of law, Zambia can create a foundation for inclusive and sustainable development, improving the lives of its citizens and positioning itself for long-term success on the global stage. On the impact of good governance and rule of law on development, the study found that good governance is the key factor for stability and security and that good governance at all levels is fundamental to economic growth, political stability and security (CSO,2013). In terms of delivering state services to the public, good governance reforms advance human rights when they improve the state's capacity to fulfil its responsibility to provide public goods which are essential for the protection of a number of human rights, such as the right to education, health and food. On the other hand, governance is important in community development in that community governance includes principles of transparency, accountability and security as poor community governance, at best leads to high out of pocket expenditure, erosion of trust in the system, reduced service utilization and poor economic growth (CSO,2011)

As regards the rule of law on development, the study found that by having a strong rule of law, a government gives business and society the stability of knowing that all rights are respected and protected and a strong rule of law should include clearly written and easily accessible laws that create certainty and enforcement of legal rights (ILO,2013). Nevertheless, the rule of law is a core principle of governance that ensures justice and fairness to all. It is a critical necessity for the survival of humanity and its absence or failure would be one of the foremost threats to the very existence of our society. The rule of law is important in Zambia in that it connotes the use of state power through rules of law for the establishment of the economic and social systems agreed upon by the people via constitutionally sanctioned representative institutions or other acceptable surrogates and above all, it calls for governance in accordance with the constitution (World Bank, 2020).

4.2.1 The Negative Effects of Language Domination

Language domination in Zambia, where English has historically held a dominant position, has given rise to several negative effects. One notable consequence is the erosion of indigenous languages and cultural diversity. The overwhelming influence of English in education, media, and official communication marginalizes local languages, diminishing their usage and endangering their preservation. (Kerapeletswe, et al. 2008) This not only weakens the connection between individuals and their cultural heritage but also perpetuates social inequalities, as proficiency in English often determines access to opportunities. Additionally, language domination can contribute to a sense of alienation and disempowerment among those who are not proficient in the dominant language. It is crucial for Zambia to recognize and address these negative effects to foster linguistic diversity, cultural richness, and inclusivity in its society. Efforts to promote and preserve indigenous languages should be prioritized to ensure a more equitable and culturally vibrant future. Moving on, the study found that the University lecturers 45% looked at foreign language as not reflecting and preserving the value and prejudices of the Zambian society. Second were the policy makers at 35% who insisted that use of foreign language as a medium of instruction and official language leads to death of local languages. Senior civil servants were at 15% who looked at people seeing less to learn their local languages while NGO’s were at 5% who saw learners not acquiring skills needed to succeed in school and in life as illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Showing Distribution of Negative Effects of Language of Domination.

On the negative effects of language domination on people’s social and educational lives, the study found that a foreign language does not reflect and preserve the value and prejudices of the society (Rice, 2009) and as suggested by the respondents, language is used to transmit values, laws, cultural norms and taboos. It should also express and reinforce culture as well as personal identity meaning a foreign language which dominates will impose its culture on the local people. They as well believed that learners fail to acquire skills they need to succeed in school and in life. Even the pupils themselves believed that the local language can help them improve their academic performance as the fully understand the materials taught to them by the teachers. Some of the advantages included; good communication between teachers and pupils due to the language, learners will be learning from known to unknown, pupils able to understand a given instruction faster and pupils have a sense of belonging since it is their language that is being used (Grenoble & Louanna, 2010). On negative

effects, people see less to learn their local languages as they are not counted as compulsory at school and are not used as criteria for getting a job. On the hand most of the respondents had a view that language domination lead to local languages death as there is gradual shift to the use of a foreign language especially in the younger generation of the Zambian speech community.

4.2.2 Foreign Language's Influence on People's Way of Thinking

In Zambia, the influence of foreign languages on people's way of thinking is a multifaceted phenomenon that reflects the country's diverse linguistic landscape and historical background. With over 70 ethnic groups and numerous local languages, Zambia has been shaped by a rich tapestry of indigenous languages. However, the impact of foreign languages, particularly English, as a legacy of colonial history, has been profound. English is the official language and is widely used in education, administration, and media. The adoption of foreign languages has not only facilitated communication across ethnic groups but has also influenced cognitive processes (Gewald et al, 2011). Exposure to different linguistic frameworks can broaden perspectives, fostering a more cosmopolitan and interconnected worldview. Additionally, the use of foreign languages, particularly in education, can influence thought patterns and contribute to the shaping of social, cultural, and economic paradigms. However, it's essential to consider the delicate balance between preserving indigenous languages and embracing foreign languages to ensure a nuanced understanding of the complex interplay between language and thought in Zambia. According to research findings, foreign language influences the Zambian people in particular and other Africans' way of thinking. The language we speak affects the way we think and the way we think affects the way we speak. Therefore, adopting a new language simply means adopting a new way of thinking and a new identity. Zambians, especially the educated take *on the* western cultural features such as practices, beliefs, way of thinking and doing things which are regarded as perfect, complete or absolute by the western themselves and unfortunately, by the educated Zambians as well. They include things such as the way of eating, clothing, religion, education systems and practices, some concepts of human rights such as homosexuality, etc which are foreign to Zambian culture and often these ideals are adopted or imposed to other civilizations especially through education, political systems and globalization (Ibid, 2010).

Many of these western ideals taught in comprehensive sexuality education such as homosexuality, lessons on the use of contraception and condoms in Zambian classes, for example can be easily detected and they can sometimes be or not opposed by the target society. In comprehensive sexuality education, learners are taught human sexuality including intimate relationships, human sexual anatomy, sexual reproduction, sexually transmitted infections, sexual activity, sexual orientation, body image and gender identity, abstinence, contraception and condoms, sexual violence prevention and reproductive rights and responsibilities which are viewed as taboos in the Zambian culture (Evans, 2010). Comprehensive sexuality education changes the way young people and adolescents perceive sex and other sex related issues which young ones are not allowed to know about in the Zambian culture. However, whether the common person, the educated one and the leader have ignored the most dangerous western ideal, language, is the main carrier of those western ideals.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it can be alleged that the negative effects of colonialism is degradation of natural resources, economic instability, ethnic rivalries, human rights violations, capitalism, urbanization, introduction of foreign diseases to livestock and humans, economic instability, distraction of traditional social, political and economic structures and trade, making the country dependent by debt accumulation and introducing a mono-cultural economy for the territory and also, by plundering Zambia's resources and carving it up into artificial ethnic boundaries as well as creating vicious cycles of hostilities among ethnic groupings, poverty and authoritarianism that are playing out to this day. Good governance is the key factor for stability and security and that good governance at all levels is fundamental to economic growth, political stability and security. In terms of delivering state services to the public, good governance reforms advance human rights when they improve the state's capacity to fulfil its responsibility to provide public goods which are essential for the protection of a number of human rights, such as the right to education, health and food. On the other hand, the rule of law is a core principle of governance that ensures justice and fairness to all. It is a critical necessity for the survival of humanity and its absence or failure would be one of the foremost threats to the very existence of our society. The rule of law is important in Zambia in that it connotes the use of state power through rules of law for the establishment of the economic and social systems agreed upon by the people via constitutionally sanctioned representative institutions or other acceptable surrogates and above all, it calls for governance in accordance with the constitution.

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6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study:

- The Government must open opportunities to every child to access quality education that will allow them address challenges in the 21st century.
- There is a need to change the philosophy and curricular and promote the teaching of science, technology and engineering.
- Zambia should not depend on developed counties to finance education but come up with policies not dependent on outsiders but on herself.
- The Government must eliminate corruption and come up with intelligent arrangements to those exploiting natural resources as well as curb illicit means so that wealth is used on behalf of the people and in the development of the country and not outside.
- Zambia need to obtain a high degree of productivity autonomy and develop an important sector of machines and industrialized raw materials and by convincing the elite from within the country to invest within the country instead of conspicuous consumption.
- Zambia should insist on value addition to raw materials, empower citizens to own industries and mines as well as exploration of minerals and should set up industries for the production of machinery, equipment and spare parts to be used in industry.
- Zambia should do away with debt traps which makes it accumulate large amounts of debt and interest and the adaptation of policies tailored to the interests of stronger countries which in a way inhibit the weaker regional counties' domestic growth, speed environmental destruction or create temporary growth that precludes sustainable development.
- The Government should come up with its own local systems that should help strengthen institutions by providing educational and technical support aimed at building strong legislature, executive and judicial system to enhance effectiveness and efficiency in governance and to further improve governance and respect for the rule of law and promotion of democratic governance.
- The Government should promote good governance and rule of law which are key factors for stability and security and that good governance and rule of law at all levels are fundamental to economic growth, political stability and security.
- The Government must do away with westernization which causes people to become more consumptive towards imported products by promoting Zambian cultures, ideals and local products.

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